

Radio Science

Supporting Data Set - 1

for the paper entitled

Observation and Analysis of Anomalous Terrestrial Diffraction as a Mechanism of Electromagnetic Precursors of Earthquakes

Masafumi Fujii

Graduate Research Division of Science and Engineering, Univ. of Toyama, Japan

Contents of this file

Radio Wave Data Observed in Toyama, Toyama Prefecture / Yatsuo, Toyama Prefecture

Introduction

This file contains the long-term observation data of the radio wave power received at the Toyama and Yatsuo observation stations in Figure 1, which provide perspectives on the normal and abnormal states of the radio wave signals and the occurrence of the earthquakes.

The data also provide a reference as to whether they are influenced by other natural environmental phenomena such as meteorological and ionospheric effects, and any radio interference from the solar activity suggested by the geomagnetic data.

The earthquake, meteorological and geomagnetic data are from the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) website. The ionospheric data are from the website of the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT), Japan. The list of earthquakes was obtained by searching the internet database of JMA using the conditions of area, magnitude and seismic intensity shown below along with Figure 2.

Period of the Radiowave Data Observed in Toyama / Yatsuo:

Toyama City, Toyama, Japan, Apr. 2019 – Mar. 2023

Yatsuo Town, Toyama, Japan, Sep. 2019 – Mar. 2023

Japan Meteorological Agency Earthquake Database Search Options:

EQ Search Area: Toyama, Ishikawa, Niigata, Gifu, Nagano (Red Regions in Figure 2)

EQ Conditions: Magnitude > 0, and Local Seismic Intensity > = 1

Figure 1 Locations of radio broadcast stations (●) and observation stations (■).

Figure 2 Region to search for earthquakes in this file: 5 prefectures near Toyama.

Observation Stations (Figure 1):

Toyama City, Toyama Pref., horizontal and vertical polarizations
(E137° 11'13", N36° 41'38", antenna altitude 30 m above sea level)

Yatsuo, Toyama City, Toyama Pref., horizontal polarization
(E137° 07'51", N36° 37'10", antenna altitude 30 m above sea level)

Radio Broadcast Stations (Figure 1):

77.4 MHz, 100 W, Iida, horizontal polarization (E137° 52'20", N35° 27'33", altitude 771 m)

80.9 MHz, no radio broadcast in Japan, referenced to monitor broadband interference.

81.9 MHz, 100 W, Suzu, vertical polarization (E137° 13'17", N37° 19'00", altitude 112 m)

82.3 MHz, 1 kW, Niigata, horizontal polarization (E138° 48'30", N37° 42'24", altitude 600 m)

86.0 MHz, 3 kW, Aomori, horizontal polarization (E140° 38'44", N40° 47'10", altitude 158 m)

88.3 MHz, 100W, Iida, horizontal polarization (E137° 52'21", N35° 27'33", altitude 771 m)

89.3 MHz, 100 W, Miyako, horizontal polarization (E142° 00'17", N39° 37'13", altitude 432 m)

Example of the Observed Data in T-1 Format (Period: Apr. 28, 2019 - Aug. 26, 2019)

[Descriptions]

JMA EQ Database information searched in the specified region with the conditions above. Local seismic intensity and magnitude are shown in ().

JMA Magnitude

Local Seismic Intensity Index in Japan

Radiowave from Miyako to Toyama

Radiowave from Iida (88.3MHz) to Toyama (V-pol. Observation)

Radiowave from Aomori to Toyama

Radiowave from Niigata (82.3MHz) to Toyama

Radiowave from Suzu (V-pol.) to Toyama (H-pol. Observation)

Frequency of No-Radiobroadcast (Measured for Detecting Noises)

Radiowave from Iida (77.4MHz) to Toyama (H-pol.)

Atmospheric Temperature (right) and Precipitation (left) in Toyama (JMA)

Ionogram of E-Layer in Kokubunji in Tokyo (NICT)

Ionogram of E-Layer in Wakkanai in Hokkaido (NICT)

Geomagnetic Field (Total Intensity) in Kakioka (JMA)

Year, Month, Date, Hour, Min in JST. Plot span is all 10 days.

Example of the Observed Data in T-2 Format (Period: Aug. 26, 2019 – Mar. 7, 2023)
 (Signals from Niigata(H) and Suzu(V) to Yatsuo(H) added.)

[Descriptions]

JMA EQ Database information searched in the specified region with the conditions above. Local seismic intensity and magnitude are shown in ().

JMA Magnitude

Local Seismic Intensity Index in Japan

Radiowave from Miyako to Toyama

Radiowave from Iida (88.3MHz) to Toyama (V-pol. Observation)

Radiowave from Aomori to Toyama

Radiowave from Niigata (82.3MHz) to Toyama

Radiowave from Niigata (82.3MHz) to Yatsuo (added)

Radiowave from Suzu (V-pol.) to Toyama (H-pol. Observation)

Radiowave from Suzu (V-pol.) to Yatsuo (H-pol. Observation, added)

Frequency of No-Radiobroadcast (Measured for Detecting Noises)

Radiowave from Iida (77.4MHz) to Toyama (H-pol.)

Atmospheric Temperature (right) and Precipitation (left) in Toyama (JMA)

Ionogram of E-Layer in Kokubunji in Tokyo (NICT)

Ionogram of E-Layer in Wakkanai in Hokkaido (NICT)

Geomagnetic Field (Total Intensity) in Kakioka (JMA)

Year, Month, Date, Hour, Min in JST. Plot span is all 10 days.

Radio Wave Data

Observed in Toyama, Toyama Prefecture / Yatsuo, Toyama Prefecture

Apr. 28, 2019 – Mar. 7, 2023

Niigata Chuetsu Dist.(2; 3.1)
Yamanashi Mid West Part(1; 2.8)

Noto Pen. Offshore(2; 3.6)
Niigata Chuetsu Dist.(1; 2.8)
Nagano South(1; 2.7)

Kanagawa West(1; 4.4)

Niigata Chuetsu Dist.(2; 2.7)
Niigata Chuetsu Dist.(1; 2.2)

Tokyo Tama East(2; 4.6)

Ishikawa Noto Dist.(1; 2.4)

EQ Mag. Epicenter (Local S.I.; Mag)

SI Local

Radiowave Power [dBm]

Precipitation [mm]

Geomag. Field [nT]

Atm. Temp. [C]

2021 11/13 00:00 2021 11/14 00:00 2021 11/15 00:00 2021 11/16 00:00 2021 11/17 00:00 2021 11/18 00:00 2021 11/19 00:00 2021 11/20 00:00 2021 11/21 00:00 2021 11/22 00:00 2021 11/23 00:00

